

Designing Multi-Faith spaces:

A delicate balance between the positive and the negative

Fig.1: Heathrow Airport multi-faith prayer room sign

Written by
Linde Rijkens

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Introduction

Definition

Multi-Faith: *“Multi-Faith is used to describe a group or space suited to meet the needs of people from different faiths”* (Paton-Falconer, 2003)

This paper will delve into the design of different airport multi-faith spaces (MFS) or multi-faith prayer rooms in the Global North, referring to the Western world, to explore the question: What are important elements in designing a multi-faith airport prayer room?

To answer this question, it is crucial to examine how to design a communal religious environment that holds significance for individuals from diverse faith traditions. Investigating the design will be done from a broader perspective to distinguish the most important elements that are involved in designing multi-faith spaces. By exploring the origin and evolution of multi-faith spaces, their purpose and functions, different approaches to designing them, as well as identifying the key expressive elements or symbolic features to incorporate into multi-faith airport prayer rooms, one can gain a comprehensive understanding of the complexities involved in creating inclusive and meaningful spaces.

Context

Due to globalization and cultural exchange, the blending of different traditions, cultures and religions has become more prevalent in the 21st century, with multi-faith prayer rooms opening in many different public buildings. *“The implementation of multi-belief/multi-faith spaces is becoming an increasing practice in a globalized world, as it addresses the need to offer spaces for worship and religious ritual in public institutions and places, such as airports and train stations, cemeteries, hospitals, prisons, military quarters, homes for the elderly, educational and recreational centres, and even in shopping malls and work centres.”* (De Velasco, 2014, p.1)

Global mobility is notably evident at airports, where travellers from different backgrounds all coexist within the same building. Passengers and staff may be looking for a quiet place, to escape the busy atmosphere for spiritual practice, thus highlighting the growing need for prayer facilities (Graham, 2009).

Origin and Evolution

In the middle of the 20th century, air travel started to become more accessible for large groups of the Western population and soon small Christian chapels in airports became widespread. In this period, there wasn't a focus on ecumenic prayer rooms (MFS) yet, however, one of the earliest steps towards a multi-faith space can be observed in Colorado, USA.

"In the 1950s, the expansion of architecture of multi-religious buildings became noticeable. An iconic example of a multi-faith chapel from this time is the Air Force Academy Cadet Chapel at the Air Force Academy in Colorado, USA. The interior of the chapel includes individual features of three religions—Catholic, Jewish, and Protestant." (Szuta 2021, p.275)

Fig.2: Air Force Academy Cadet Chapel at the Air Force Academy, Colorado. Sketches by A.F.Szuta based on photos from A.Perez (2010)

This airport had set up multiple chapels for different religions in one building and even though separated in to different areas, the three religions all shared the same roof. At this point in time, the prayer rooms were primarily intended for personnel rather than for travellers.

In the late 1960s, Catholic airport chapels gradually transformed into Protestant and multi-faith places during the 1970s and 1980s, and later evolved into religiously inclusive spaces in the 1990s and 2000s, with prayer rooms predominantly being utilized by visitors since the early 90s. *"They began to function rather as more private, intimate spaces/rooms for individual focus, silence, or personal prayer"* (Szuta 2021, p.275), referring to the use of ecumenic prayer rooms from the '90s on.

The early 2000s witnessed the rise of more religiously inclusive spaces that can be used by people of 'all faiths, or none' with the renaming of chapels to 'prayer rooms' in order to convey a name that is free from on-going conflicts and politics (Cadge, 2018).

Designing a multi-faith prayer room

The wide range of user profiles of multi-faith prayer rooms requires the design and management of these places to be inclusive for all users, while still meeting the essential minimal criteria expected by each religion.

“The design of MFS must deal with geographical orientation (a relevant issue for religions like Islam, Judaism and Orthodox Christianity)...separation of genders, and hygiene needs, among other questions. Neutrality (and the avoidance of religio-centric premises) therefore is the main issue to be taken into consideration for the design of those kinds of spaces, even if perfect neutrality will not be possible.” (De Velasco, 2014, p.1)

In his theoretical proposals for multi-faith prayer rooms, Velasco outlines the basic requirements that each multi-faith space should follow, stating that designs allowing easy adaptation and presenting a certain harmony are most favourable.

Square layouts are preferred as orientation is less defined compared to a rectangular floor plan as well as making it easy to determine the direction of Jerusalem or the East, which are important to Judaism and the Islam. The room’s size is important to consider, as they *“can not be too ridiculous proportions, as this might be dissuasive, since decorum is a key factor in worship.” (De Velasco, 2014, p.7)*

Having a cloakroom for visitors, as well as a storage room where objects and materials needed for worship can be placed, is another element that should be considered. Religions that require the separation of worship space for various reasons, such as the division of genders in Judaism, should have access to a moveable folding screen. Furthermore, followers of Islam, need to have access to a location with running water as it is necessary for them to cleanse before engaging in prayer. Additionally, providing furniture where shoes can be placed is important for faiths that typically sit on the floor. An interesting response to the mix of different religions is De Velasco’s concept of dividing the multi-faith prayer room to solve conflicting design requirements. De Velasco suggested splitting religions into two rooms, one for faiths that like to sit on chairs or benches, such as Christianity, and the other for faiths that typically sit directly on the floor and remove footwear before entering, such as Buddhism or Islam.

Finally, noise can lead to rejection and may even result in the stigmatisation of users and thus soundproofing should be included to make sure practicing religion stays in a private sphere.

The requirements above demonstrate that the combination of different faiths in one room requires skilful coordination. The diversity makes these places challenging to handle in a way that satisfies everyone.

Positive and Negative design

The coexistence of multiple faiths within a single room often leads to a 'negative design'. This term has been introduced by researcher Andrew Crompton, who in his 2013 publication 'God Leaves the Building', identified two contrasting styles: the positive and the negative. *"In the positive type images and artefacts from different faiths are on open view and we have unity by inclusion. In the negative type rival images are either absent or kept separate and we have unity by exclusion."* (Crompton, 2013, p.479).

Negative design

Fig.3: Heathrow Terminal 2 multifaith prayer room

Positive design

Fig.4: Ecumenical Chapel Katowice–Pyrzowice Airport

Apart from the basic religious requirements outlined above, there are no architectural guidelines for the construction and design of multi-faith spaces. However, the majority of today's multi-faith spaces in the Global North follow similar stylistic patterns and can be categorized into the minimal, negative approach and the positive or maximalist approach.

Negative Design

Establishing an inclusive atmosphere that accommodates multiple religious beliefs without showing preference towards any particular one is a difficult task. How does one design without displaying favouritism? The result in negative design has architecture that functions as ambient noise rather than a central focus. As Crompton states, *"Empty white rooms have become the default solution because there is an assumption that we should not be exposed to symbols of other people's faith if that can be avoided. (...) A multifaith room cannot afford to look like a church or a mosque or a temple. Nor should it have a style associated with something non-religious or national. Nor should it be modernist if that projects a secular or scientific outlook."* (2013, p.474).

In her research, A.F. Szuta examined the multi-faith airport prayer rooms in Poland and determined that they consistently display unfavourable cases of negative design. An empty white space with inadequate illumination and a complete absence of windows typically characterises these rooms, as well as lacking a clear axis. These designs fail to foster unity or peace (Szuta, 2021).

Crompton adds on this in his 2015 exploration of negative design, *“Being minimally meaningful is not the same as being minimal... being unspecific does not come easily to architects who pride themselves on their ability to create meaningful concepts and write specifications. Utterly empty rooms seem sinister, yet whatever is added to them causes problems; any table can become an altar, every bowl of pebbles seems pagan. This is the trap in which the designer is caught.”* (Crompton 2015, p.28).

Following up in 2016, in ‘Religion, Equalities and Inequalities’ Crompton and Hewson (2016) describe multi-faith as a social intervention, arguing that multi-faith Spaces *“follow the modern preference for ‘faith’ rather than ‘religion’ and facilitate personal acts of worship”, acting “as a benign form of social control, treating religion as a disorder to be tidied away”* (pp.80-81). This negative approach has resulted in numerous issues. Attempting to appeal to a broad audience led to a lack of specific appeal and sense of impermanence.

Nevertheless, spaces designed in a negative style are not entirely bad and also have advantages. *“They are considered to be ‘safe’ because of their neutralization through whiteness, and the maximally reduced number of religious objects reduces the chances of violating someone's privacy in faith, thereby interfering in their religion.”*(Szuta, 2021, p.280). Furthermore, Crompton’s 2015 perspective suggests that the sacred and profane are situational, not fixed in categories. *“What is being emplaced in multi-faith spaces is being carried into the room on bodies and clothes rather than represented architecturally.”* (Crompton, 2015, p.29) Individuals contribute to the sacredness with their presence, prayers and actions and thus the profane emerges when people enter the space, rather than it being present before.

A well-executed negative design can be seen at the University of Toronto. This multi-faith centre aimed to create a *“faith-neutral space with a design aesthetic that is universally perceived as a sanctuary and retreat for all while simultaneously creating innovative elements that allow all faith groups to transform the spaces quickly, so as to suit particular needs.”* (Architizer, 2016). With the use of natural materials, as well as the expression of light with the transparent onyx walls and ceiling, the space creates a calming atmosphere. *“This room does not evoke associations with any particular religion, and it speaks to spirituality and arouses a sense of social unity and peace.”* (Szuta, 2021, p.278). This makes it one of the only negative designed Multi-faith prayer rooms that actually reaches their goal of designing a faith neutral space.

Fig.5 & Fig.6: Multi-Faith Centre, University of Toronto (Architizer, 2016)

Airport prayer rooms serve a different function than Multi-faith centres, being more focussed on rest and prayer rather than events. Still, there can be inspiration taken from the architecture of Toronto's multi-Faith centre, showing that the design can be more than the safe, but bland, white box that has become the standard. Even though a truly negative design is hard to achieve, the airport prayer rooms require proper design and shouldn't be treated as an afterthought.

Positive Design

The less commonly used design style is positive design. Designing a positive space is considered more challenging due to being more prone to missteps. Designing by adding needs to be well thought-out in symbolism and harmony, as a cluster of different iconography can be inappropriate for inclusive, multi-faith designs. For example: the Bimah is exclusively important to Judaism and a cross is strongly tied to Christianity, but a cross can be conflicting with Judaism decorating as they often include arcs and curves to avoid lines from crossing (Paton-Falconer, 2003).

"In early multi-faith spaces you can find shelves of artefacts like religious supermarkets with ludicrous juxtapositions such as statuettes of Christ next to witch's cauldrons, prayer rugs next to fire-worship equipment. Crosses, it turns out, are offensive to nearly everyone and where they survive they are disguised, often by being bent into airplane shape." (Crompton, 2016, p.28).

This raises the question, what elements can be incorporated in a positive design without being insensitive to others?

"However much religions have in common, in the end they never prove to be wholly like one another. Not concentric at all, each emerges as eccentric, making its distinctive statement in its own language. And where the eccentricities occur, there the religions find their definitions, their distinctive qualities." (Jackson, 2003, p.333).

While religions may share similarities, they express their faith differently. Paton-Falconer (2003) researches these differences and similarities in the religious landscapes of Judaism, Hinduism, Buddhism, Christianity and Islam.

Paton-Falconer analyses and compares by using semiotics: A sign can be called a 'signifier', meaning how it is being observed, and 'signified' refers to the meaning of said sign (Barthes, 1967). For example, a red traffic light is an electric object that shines light in the colour red (signifier), however, the meaning communicates that you need to stop driving (signified). These semiotics can also be used to design a multi-faith space.

Are there religious symbols that have meaning in multiple faiths that can be used to find common ground, even if they perhaps have different connotations for each religion? Given that different religions might interpret the same pattern or symbol in different ways, it is not crucial for the meanings or symbols to be shared by all religions with Paton-Falconer stating *"For example, the square is an important religious symbolic form; in Buddhism, it can signify moral restraint, In Christianity. the New Jerusalem as described in Revelation, in Hinduism, the heavens. Although all of these individual meanings and associations are different, the square is still a square. It is important to these religions regardless of the variations of meaning and that is what is significant."* (2003, p.31). The research conducts that *"Some items are too closely connected to a particular religion to be used successfully in what attempts to be an entirely inclusive design solution."* (Paton-Falconer, 2003, p.131). Nonetheless, the following items are of high value for multi-faith landscape design: columns or pillars, domed or vaulted ceilings, light, squares, vegetation, mounts, water, stone, threshold, enclosure and verticality. Falconer's study also found that the idea of transcendence is deemed to be important in all religions. Even though the aforementioned items hold different meanings and significance to the individual religions, they share the same signifiers.

Nevertheless, it is not appropriate to merely place these symbols within a given space and consider the task complete, this can unintentionally create favouritism with Crompton noting: *"Many multi-faith rooms have abstract artworks based on sea and sky, bowls of pebbles or bare branches artfully arranged. The difficulty is that nature, especially picturesque nature, is not culturally neutral. When presented in a religious setting without any other religious symbols to modify it, it produces a New Age, or even a pagan atmosphere."* (Crompton, 2013, p.482).

However, Paton-Falconer (2003) found that the unifying concept across religions is transcendence, which is often symbolised by light as a representation of life and a divine presence. The ephemeral nature of light can be created by advanced, modern technology or natural light can be altered to create various light impressions, enhancing the atmosphere and generating emotional resonance beyond its basic function of illuminating a space. Another feature to symbolise transcendence is the verticality of a room. Christian Norberg Schultz, an architectural theorist, regarded verticality as the sacred aspect of space since the vertical axis connects the ground with the sky, and creates a focal point where all horizontal movement ceases. As long as men remains on land and is bound to the Earth, the vertical

direction is an essential as well as fundamental aspect: crucial for stability, structure, movement, and orientation, in other words, it is vital for life and can symbolize the upward climb towards the light (Norberg-Schulz, 2000).

Examining the statements and theories posited by researchers above, it can be inferred that an effective positive multi-faith environment is one emphasized by the use of height and luminosity. However, this inclination then inevitably reverts back to the characterization of the negative style.

The future of multi-faith spaces

In the existing multi-functional spaces two categories of design styles were distinguished: the positive and the negative design styles. It is noteworthy that there is no definitive or incorrect approach when it comes to designing the multi-faith prayer rooms as religion is of subjective nature. In "The Varieties of Religious Experience" philosopher William James explains *'Religion, therefore, as I ask you take it, shall mean for us the feelings, acts, and experiences of individual men in their solitude, so far as they apprehend themselves to stand in relation to whatever they may consider the divine.'* (James, 1902, p.36), suggesting faith is about individual experiences, beliefs and feelings, emphasizing the subjective nature and personal perspective.

Additionally, French existentialist Jean Paul Sartre emphasizes individual freedom and responsibility in creating meaning in life in his writings. *"Life has no meaning a priori. It is up to you to give it a meaning, and value is nothing but the meaning that you choose."* (Mueller and Sartre, 1947). From this standpoint, the meaning of life and the significance of spaces are not inherently or objectively established, but rather shaped by individuals based on their distinct perspectives, experiences, backgrounds, cultural settings, and beliefs. Thus, the individuals' interpretations of environments and their designs are influenced by their personal preferences.

Therefore, a space designed to promote unity by inclusion may be perceived positively by some while others may interpret it negatively. Similarly, a space designed to promote unity through exclusion can also be viewed as both favourable and unfavourable.

Perhaps the best way to go forward is to strive for a kind of balance, as suggested by Crompton (2015). Crompton notes that there is a need for a more general, neutral design that is not insensitive. A way forward could be a mixture of both negative and positive design styles, aiming to find a way to inclusivity by harmonizing the plurality of beliefs. In short, combining the most favourable aspects of both architectural types to create a multifunctional space might lead to an inspiring place, where travellers feel comfortable, experience devotion, and can practice their own religion in private.

Conclusion

Looking back at the positive and negative design styles, one can see different strengths and weaknesses in both styles. Positive designs creating inclusivity by adding symbolism can be perceived favourable, but can very easily go from harmony to an offensive chaotic cluster of icons, or leaning too heavily on nature elements and thereby overshadowing certain religions. Meanwhile, negative designs are a safer design style in that regard. The minimalism makes sure it doesn't favour or offend but then in return, the emptiness can be perceived as meaningless.

However, the multi-faith centre in Toronto showed that a neutral multi-faith centre can be successful. With the proper thought and design, a minimal but meaningful space had been created, which could be used as inspiration for designing airport multi-faith spaces in the future. By integrating the strengths of both negative and positive design styles, rooms may achieve a state of harmony amidst different beliefs. multifunctional spaces that inspire comfort, devotion, and privacy for travellers practising their own religions.

Nevertheless, the perception of a space and its value is subjective, shaped by individual perspectives and values. Additionally, religion is a different concept for everyone and thereby determining the design of a multi-faith space is difficult to achieve. The question 'What are important elements in designing a multi-faith space' is then paradoxical to answer as it is subjective and thereby what makes a design good or bad is up to each individual's interpretation.

Illustrations

Fig.1: Heathrow Airport has Multi Faith Prayer Rooms in every terminal (Image: Tkkurikawa via Getty) (no date) Getreading. <https://www.getreading.co.uk/whats-on/whats-on-news/heathrow-airports-prayer-rooms-those-24443962>. (Image: Tkkurikawa via Getty)

Fig.2: A. Perez (2010) AD Classics: USAFA Cadet Chapel/Walter Netsch of Skidmore, Owings, & Merrill, Available online at: <https://www.archdaily.com/>

Fig.3: Multi-faith Prayer Room, Heathrow Terminal 2 (2016) Flickr. <https://www.flickr.com/photos/stml/24613543702>.

Fig.4: Ecumenical Chapel in Katowice–Pyrzkowice Airport (photo by Soptysek). (no date). <https://www.sciencedirect.com.ucreative.idm.oclc.org/science/article/pii/S2095263521000054?via%3Dihub>.

Fig.5: Multi-Faith Centre, University of Toronto by Moriyama Teshima Architects (2016). <https://architizer.com/projects/multi-faith-centre-university-of-toronto/>.

Fig.6: Multi-Faith Centre, University of Toronto by Moriyama Teshima Architects (2016). <https://architizer.com/projects/multi-faith-centre-university-of-toronto/>.

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